

CERTIFICATE OF PARTICIPATION

This is to certify that

Ranwa Khorsheed

presented in the

24th Warwick International Conference

In Applied Linguistics

28-30 June, 2022

Department of Applied Linguistics, University of Warwick

Sincerely,

Professor Ema Ushioda
Head of Department
Applied Linguistics
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24th WICAL
Organising Committee
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